

Removal of basic dyes from aqueous solution using Sone sand as an adsorbent

S. D. Khattri* and M. K. Singh

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, India

Manuscript received 14 December 1998, revised 26 April 1999, accepted 17 May 1999

The potentiality of Sone sand from the Sone river, Sonbhadra, Uttar Pradesh (India) has been investigated as effective adsorbent to remove the dyes from aqueous solutions. The effects of different types of dyes, particle diameter of the adsorbent, dye concentration, pH of the solution and temperature on the best available adsorbent have been evaluated. The dynamics of adsorbate transport from bulk to the solid phase has been studied at different temperatures. The applicability of Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm suggests the formation of monolayer coverage of the dye molecules on outer surface of the adsorbent. The thermodynamics of dye-sand system indicates spontaneous and exothermic nature of the process. Various thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated.

Adsorption of dye (astrazone blue) on Sorbsil silica has been investigated¹. The use of fuller's earth and fired clay appeared to be more efficient and attractive adsorbent compared to expensive materials like silica and carbon². Buffing dust generated from leather industry can be considered as a source for obtaining activated carbon for the removal of dyes from wastewater³. The ability of heterogeneous mixture of alumina-clay (1 : 2)⁴ and some bioadsorbent^{5,6} to remove the colour of dyes has been investigated. Keeping above in view it was planned to devise a suitable and cheap method for the treatment of water and wastewater by adsorption technique using unconventional absorbent such as Sone sand collected from the Sone river, Uttar Pradesh (India).

The present work deals with investigations of adsorption studies on Sone sand using dyes (methylene blue and malachite green) at different temperatures and pH. The adsorption dynamics and thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

The chemical analysis and X-ray diffraction data of Sone sand are presented in Table 1. The Sone sand used is rich in metal oxides. These oxides when mixed with the dye solution undergo surface hydroxylation which give negatively charged surface. The surface complex is formed at the adsorbate-adsorbent interface owing to the interaction of the negatively charged surface and dye cations.

Effect of contact time and concentration : Fig. 1 shows that the amount of dye adsorbed in the aqueous solution increased with time and achieved equilibrium in 35 min and is different for each concentration, indicating independent nature of equilibrium period. A series of contact experiments were undertaken for varying initial dye concentrations (6, 8

and 12 mg dm⁻³). For low concentrations, there was a rapid uptake of dye due to surface mass transfer. The removal of the dye, methylene blue and malachite green by the Sone sand was found to increase from 1.057 to 1.767 mg g⁻¹ (88.12–73.64%) and 0.999 to 1.723 mg g⁻¹ (83.25–71.80%) respectively, by increasing concentration from 6 to 12 mg dm⁻³ at a temperature 30° and pH 7.5. This shows that removal of the dye is highly concentration-dependent. The removal curves were found to be smooth and continuous indicating the formation of monolayer coverage of the adsorbate on the outer surface of the adsorbent⁷.

Effect of particle size : The adsorption of dyes, methylene blue and malachite green from solution of concentration 8 mg dm⁻³ was found to increase from 71.58 to 87.35% and 67.03 to 84.72% respectively, with decrease in particle

Fig. 1. Effect of concentration on the removal of methylene blue and malachite green by the Sone sand; temp. = 30 ± 1°, pH = 7.5.

Table 1. Chemical analysis and X-ray diffraction data of the Sone sand

Constituent	Chemical analysis		X-ray diffraction Possible mineral
	% by wt.	d (Å)	
SiO ₂	96.76	4.2655	α-Quartz
		3.3413	α-Quartz
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.23	4.456	α-Quartz
		2.2347	α-Quartz
Al ₂ O ₃	0.83	1.8159	α-Quartz
		1.5405	α-Quartz
CaO	0.13	1.4182	α-Quartz
Loss on ignition	1.05	3.66	Hematite
		1.3514	Hematite
		2.1259	Kaolinite
		1.386	Kaolinite
		1.451	Calcite

size of the adsorbent from 50 to 100 mesh at 30°.

Adsorption dynamics : The overall rate constant for adsorption (k_{ad} , min⁻¹) of the methylene blue was evaluated in the light of Lagergren rate equation⁸,

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{k_{ad}}{2.303} t$$

where q and q_e are the amounts of adsorbate (mg g⁻¹) at time t (min) and at equilibrium respectively. The values of k_{ad} at different temperatures, calculated from the slopes of the respective linear plots of $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t , are presented in Table 2. It may be concluded from the values of k_{ad} that the reaction taking place is of the first order.

The rate constants of intra-particle diffusion (k_p) at different temperatures were determined using Weber and Moris relationship⁹, $q = k_p t^{1/2}$, by plotting amount of dye adsorbed versus square-root of time. The values of k_p obtained from the slopes of the respective plots are included in Table 2. The results reveal that the initial part of these plots are straight-lines at 25, 35 and 45° which do not pass through the origin, showing that the intra-particle diffusion is not the only rate-controlling step¹⁰.

Table 2. Adsorption kinetic parameters for methylene blue and malachite green at different temperatures

Temp. °C	Methylene blue			Malachite green		
	10 ⁻² k_{ad}	k_p	K	10 ⁻² k_{ad}	k_p	K
	(mg g ⁻¹ min ^{-1/2})			(mg g ⁻¹ min ^{-1/2})		
25	4.60	0.20	5.99	4.37	0.18	4.89
35	4.31	0.17	4.08	4.20	0.17	3.54
45	4.16	0.16	3.16	3.94	0.16	2.81

Effect of temperature : The amount of dye, methylene blue and malachite green adsorbed decreased from 1.370 to 1.215 mg g⁻¹ (85.68–75.93%) and 1.328 to 1.180 mg g⁻¹ (83.04–73.75%) respectively, with the rise of temperature of the dye solutions from 25 to 45°. This shows the exothermic nature of the process. The decrease in adsorption with rise of temperature may be due to the enhanced escaping tendency of the dye molecules from the surface of adsorbent. This was again confirmed by the thermodynamic parameters. The negative values of ΔG° (Table 3) are indicative of spontaneous nature of the process. The negative ΔH° values at different temperatures also confirm the exothermic nature of the process. The negative values of ΔS° suggest the probability of favourable adsorption.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for methylene blue and malachite green

Temp. °C	Methylene blue			Malachite green		
	- ΔG°	- ΔH°	- ΔS°	- ΔG°	- ΔH°	- ΔS°
	kJ mol ⁻¹ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹			kJ mol ⁻¹ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹		
25	4.43	29.30	83.46	3.93	24.72	69.77
35	3.60	20.93	56.26	3.24	18.81	50.56
45	3.04	-	-	2.73	-	-

Adsorption isotherm : To study the validity of Freundlich adsorption isotherm¹¹, the following equation has been used,

$$\frac{x}{m} = K_F C_e^{1/n}$$

The linear plot of $\log x/m$ vs $\log C_e$ indicates the applicability of the Freundlich adsorption isotherm for the present system which exhibits a monolayer coverage of the adsorbate on the outer surface of the adsorbent.

The experimental data for the uptake of the dyes methylene blue and malachite green by the Sone sand at 25, 35 and 45° have been correlated with the rearranged Langmuir's model of adsorption¹²,

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{Q^\circ b} + \frac{C_e}{Q^\circ}$$

The linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e at different temperatures suggest the applicability of Langmuir isotherm for the present system. The values of Q° and b at different temperatures were determined from the slopes and intercepts of the respective plots and are presented in Table 4. The equilibrium parameter, R_L , is represented as follows¹³,

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + bC_0}$$

R_L values between 0 and 1 indicate favourable adsorption

for all the initial concentrations and temperatures studied (Table 4).

Table 4. Langmuir constants for methylene blue and malachite green

Temp. °C	Methylene blue			Malachite green		
	Q° mg g ⁻¹	b L mg ⁻¹	R_L	Q° mg g ⁻¹	b L mg ⁻¹	R_L
25	2.64	1.61	0.07	2.32	1.51	0.08
35	2.34	0.99	0.11	2.19	0.97	0.11
45	2.16	0.91	0.12	2.05	0.86	0.13

Effect of pH : The Sone sand proved to be effective adsorbent for the removal of dye from aqueous solution at pH 7.5, at which almost quantitative adsorption was achieved. With the increase of pH from 4.5 to 7.5, the uptake of methylene blue and malachite green increased from 62.89 to 73.64 and 58.25 to 71.80% respectively, by the Sone sand at temperature 30° and concentration 12 mg dm⁻³ of the dyes. This is attributed to the increasing electronegative charge on the adsorbent as the pH of the solution is increased¹⁴. As the adsorbent surface is negatively charged in presence of OH⁻ the increasing electrostatic attraction between positive adsorbate (Dye²⁺) species and negative adsorbent particles (Sone sand) would lead to increased adsorption of the dyes¹⁵

Conclusion : The Sone sand is an effective adsorbent for the removal of the dyes. The fitness of Langmuir and Freundlich models shows the formation of monolayer coverage of the adsorbate at the outer surface of the adsorbent and the process is exothermic in nature. The mechanism involves an initial rapid rate for the dye-removal due to surface adsorption followed by intra-particle diffusion which is not only rate-controlling step.

Experimental

Methylene blue and malachite green (Sandoz) were used. Sone sand samples collected from the Sone river (district Sonbhadra, Uttar Pradesh, India) was boiled with concentrated HCl to remove surface impurities and then washed with boiling water repeatedly till free from chloride ions. The sample was dried, activated at 400° for 4 h, allowed to cool and sieved for particles of 50, 80 and 100 mesh size.

Batch adsorption experiments were carried out by shaking the adsorbent Sone sand (1 g) with aqueous solution

(200 ml) of the dye of desired concentration at different temperatures and pH at a constant speed in a water thermostat ($\pm 1^{\circ}$). At different intervals of time, samples were drawn out and the dye concentration was measured colorimetrically using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 160 A) at λ_{\max} 664 and 616 nm. The effects of different parameters on the adsorption of various dyes using the adsorbent were investigated.

Acknowledgement

Necessary facilities provided by the Head, Chemistry Department, Banaras Hindu University, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. G. McKay, M. S. Otterburn and A. G. Sweeney, *Water Res.*, 1981, **15**, 327.
2. G. McKay, M. S. Otterburn and J. A. Aga, *Water Air Soil Pollut.*, 1985, **24**, 307.
3. G. Sekaran, K. A. Shanmugasundaram, M. Mariappan and K. V. Raghavan, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 1995, **2**, 311.
4. S. D. Khattri and M. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 1998, **5**, 230.
5. S. D. Khattri and M. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 1999, **6**, 120.
6. S. D. Khattri and M. K. Singh, *Adsorption Sci. Technol.*, accepted.
7. G. S. Gupta, G. Prasad, K. K. Pandey and V. N. Singh, *Water Air Soil Pollut.*, 1988, **37**, 13.
8. S. K. Khare, K. K. Pandey, R. M. Srivastava and V. N. Singh, *J. Chem. Tech. Biotechnol.*, 1987, **30**, 99.
9. W. J. Weber, Jr. and J. C. Morris, *J. Sanit Eng. Div. Am. Civ. Engrs.*, 1964, **90**, 79.
10. V. J. P. Poots, G. McKay and J. J. Healy, *Water Res.*, 1976, **10**, 1061.
11. H. Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", Methuen, London, 1926.
12. I. Langmuir, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 1361.
13. G. McKay, M. S. Otterburn and A. G. Sweeny, *Water Res.*, 1980, **14**, 15.
14. C. P. Huang and W. Stumm, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1973, **43**, 409.
15. G. Y. Onada and D. W. Fuerstenau, "Proceeding of 7th International Mineral Processing Congress", New York, 1964.